

Librarians' ICT Proficiency and Awareness of Artificial Intelligence for Information Resources Management in Nigerian Libraries

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Abstract

Keywords: ICT Proficiency, Awareness of Artificial Intelligence, Information Resources Management

Introduction: This paper investigated librarians' ICT proficiency and awareness of artificial intelligence for information resources management in Nigerian libraries.

Method: the study adopted a descriptive correlational design through quantitative approach. A survey was used to gather information from 399 librarians from Nigerian university libraries. The study adopted both descriptive statistic of frequency count and inferential statistics of multiple regression analysis using SPSS, v-27.

Results/Findings: The study indicates that librarians had a high ICT proficiency, especially in accessing online resources and using metadata standards, though proficiency levels vary, a moderate level of awareness among librarians regarding various AI applications in IRM, with consistent awareness of collaborative filtering and variable awareness of named entity recognition and sentiment analysis., the study further revealed that ICT proficiency of librarians has a significant positive effect on information resource management while awareness of artificial intelligence does not significantly impact information resource management.

Conclusion: The study concludes that librarians generally exhibit high ICT proficiency, particularly in accessing online resources and using metadata standards, though proficiency levels vary. There is moderate awareness of AI applications, with consistent awareness of collaborative filtering and variable awareness of named entity recognition and sentiment analysis.

Recommendations: Libraries should implement practical AI training for librarians, focusing on tools like named entity recognition and sentiment analysis, and build on their strong ICT skills with advanced training in digital cataloguing, online resource access, and electronic resource management. Libraries should invest in AI-driven search technologies to enhance search accuracy and efficiency, and employ data analytics to understand user behaviour and preferences, guiding collection development and improving services.

Introduction

Information Resources Management (IRM) is crucial for Nigerian libraries, optimizing resource utilization and enhancing access through efficient cataloging, classification, and digital integration (Lawal, 2021). It improves user experience with automated systems and customized services, provides data analytics for decision-making, preserves cultural heritage through archiving and digitization, ensures compliance with international standards, and promotes staff development through training (Evans & Schonfeld, 2020). Ultimately, IRM contributes to the sustainability and relevance of libraries in the modern information landscape.

Librarians' competency in information and communication technology (ICT) skills is critical for effective management of information resources in the ever-changing field of modern librarianship (Oyovwe-Tinuoye, et al., 2021). As custodians of knowledge resources, librarians are responsible for curating, arranging, and disseminating information to meet the diverse needs of library users. The success of this mandate depends on librarians' effective use of ICT tools, advanced skills in internet research, email management, web browsing, and Microsoft Office software. (Kumar, et al., 2023).

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into library operations is considered necessary, and increase the librarians' skill to fully transform the management of information resources (Owolabi et al., 2020). Algorithms like Natural Language Processing (NLP), which include techniques such as Named Entity Recognition (NER) and Sentiment Analysis, provide ways to automate processes such as categorising and analysing user input. This helps optimise the organisation of resources and improve service quality (Ali, Naeem, & Bhatti, 2020). Collaborative filtering algorithms provide personalised recommendation systems,

improving user experience by offering customised ideas derived from borrowing history and preferences (Ajani et al., 2022).

Clustering algorithms help librarians organise similar items and optimise resource searches. Virtual assistants or chatbots improve library services by providing immediate support and enhancing accessibility (Oladokun, et al., 2023). Computer vision algorithms aid in digitising physical materials and analysing them, supporting preservation efforts and resource accessibility (Alimov, 2022). Sentiment analysis and anomaly detection provide insights into user preferences and operational issues, enabling data-driven decisions and fraud detection. Time series forecasting predicts future resource demands, aiding strategic collection building and resource allocation.

Nigerian libraries are undergoing digital transformation, and understanding AI can enhance information management and library services nationwide (Owolabi et al., 2022). Despite ICT and AI's benefits, practical application is hindered by librarians' inadequate skills due to insufficient training, resources, and institutional support (Adegboro & Omowumi, 2021). This skill gap leads to inefficiencies and limited access to services, affecting patron satisfaction (Mommoh & Abubakar, 2019). Librarians must stay updated on AI trends and ICT proficiency to contribute to technological advancements in libraries (Bonesso, Gerli, & Cortellazzo, 2019; Toyese, Oyedokun, & Laaro, 2018). Evaluating and improving librarians' AI skills is essential for better service and user satisfaction in Nigeria (Yoon, et al., 2021). Therefore, this study examined the proficiency of librarians in using information and communication technology (ICT), determined their level of awareness of artificial intelligence and determined the effectiveness of information resources management. The study also hypothesised to test the influence of ICT proficiency of

librarians and their awareness of artificial intelligence on the effectiveness of information resources management in Nigerian universities.

Literature Review

The need for librarians to possess expertise in ICT, make use of artificial intelligence for managing information resources, and enhance information resources management for maximum user satisfaction has become crucial, prominent, and indispensable in today's competitive landscape of information dissemination. In the following sections we examine the information resource management based on the perspective of scholars to appreciate the dimension and the ICT and artificial intelligence requirement. We demonstrate that the roles of libraries and librarians are in need of artificial intelligence to leverage efficiency in service provision with the high competence in ICT by librarians.

Information Resources Management

Information Resources Management (IRM) in libraries involves strategic management of various information resources, including physical collections, digital repositories, databases, and electronic resources. The goal is to ensure their efficient utilisation, accessibility, and long-term preservation (Rahman et al., 2023). This comprehensive approach involves selecting, acquiring, organizing, managing circulation, providing reference services, preserving digital content, licensing resources, engaging users, and evaluating services (Singh, 2023; Redkina, 2023; Oleksandr & Nadiia, 2023). Libraries can leverage technology and innovations to enhance user experiences, improve information access, and adapt to user preferences, promoting academic excellence, personal growth, and the overall improvement of the information ecosystem. (Sokil & Zvorskyi, 2023; Olubiyo, 2023; Terentiev, 2023).

IRM is the systematic process of acquiring, assessing, and preserving physical and digital resources to meet user needs. It involves selecting content based on user preferences, curriculum, and institutional objectives (Kuzminova & Ilin, 2023). . Efficient cataloguing and metadata management are crucial for organising library materials, while digital IRM manages digital repositories, databases, e-journals, and e-books, including licensing, access management, content preservation, and copyright compliance (Agu, 2018; Ross, 2012). The implementation of an all-encompassing strategy for Information Resource Management (IRM) guarantees the efficient management and arrangement of digital resources, particularly as libraries progressively shift towards digital formats (Agu, 2018).

IRM is crucial for enabling efficient and user-friendly access to information resources through various channels like online catalogues, discovery platforms, and library websites (Kumar, 2023; Sokil & Zvorskyi, 2023; Agbo & Eyinnah, 2023).

IRM evaluates library services, collections, and resources using user input, statistics, surveys, and industry benchmarks to identify improvement areas (Liu, 2022). Libraries utilise AI, machine learning, and data analytics for efficient information retrieval, personalised services, and improved operational performance (Wang et al., 2021; Kapterev, 2023; Alwiyah & Salamah, 2023).. Big data mining techniques analyze digital resource access logs to extract user preferences, leading to improved user experiences and efficient resource utilization.

Librarians' ICT Proficiency

Librarians must be proficient in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to facilitate access to information resources and help users navigate the digital landscape (Ogunmodede et al., 2023; Olubiyo, 2023; Khumalo, 2023). The adoption of ICT has

transformed librarianship, emphasizing the need for ongoing training and skill development (Khumalo, 2023). In a competitive marketplace, librarians need to understand consumer needs, communicate effectively, and provide efficient services (Sergeevich, 2023). Incorporating ICTs in digital literacy training enhances students' digital literacy skills and facilitates effective information retrieval in a technology-driven society.

Digital libraries are crucial for academic and research institutions, offering advanced systems for preserving, retrieving, and distributing documents, thus revolutionizing operations (Velmurugan, 2023). Research highlights the importance of librarians' digital literacy skills for effective digital literacy training (Lopatina & Grushevskaya, 2023; Khumalo, 2023) and proficiency in various reading strategies, online research methodologies, and critical assessment of digital information sources (Cheung et al., 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the need for librarians to adeptly use digital resources, leading to global collaborations and innovative online initiatives that showcase the crucial role of libraries and librarians (Sibiya, 2023; Velmurugan, 2023).

Strong digital literacy skills enable librarians to navigate online databases, evaluate digital resources, and stay updated on emerging technologies, while contemporary librarians should possess diverse abilities for effective digital collections management (Sibiya, 2023). The Fourth Industrial Revolution has shifted library and information science, emphasizing the need for librarians with digital scholarship knowledge for curation, preservation, and effective information-seeking (Cheung et al., 2023). Moreover, the significance of librarians in Open Science is emphasised, retraining the need for training to maximise Open Access possibilities and advocate for the advantages of Open Science for society (Tolmach, 2022).

The development and retention of ICT skills among librarians encounter obstacles such as insufficient training prospects, restricted resource availability, and a dearth of institutional backing (Ubogu, 2022; Uyun, 2022). According to recent reports by Nazim et al. (2022) and Tolmach (2022), librarians in Nigeria and India have demonstrated above-average proficiency in information and communication technology (ICT). However, they lack the proficiency and necessary expertise to effectively manage ICT-based operations and services so as to remain up-to-date with emerging technologies (Guzenok & Begisheva, 2022; Kushwah & Shrivastava, 2022). The role of librarians is undergoing a transformation in the context of digitalization, necessitating a significant focus on digital literacy and proficiency. This entails the requirement for well-organised training programmes and modifications to the curriculum to align with the current dynamics of information and communication technology (Naik et al., 2022).

Awareness of artificial intelligence by librarians for information resources management

Research on awareness of artificial intelligence (AI) for managing information resources among librarians varies in location, library types and outcomes. Pakistani academic librarians utilize AI technologies like NLP and cloud services, but lack awareness of robotics and chatbots, suggesting potential for further expansion (Ali et al., 2020)., while in Tanzania, awareness with low adoption rate (Bakiri, Mbembati, & Tinabo, 2024). In Nigeria, awareness of AI has been reported in some studies, however, the adoption is hampered by various challenges such as “potential loss of job, high risk of maintenance, inadequate internet service provision, technical problems, epileptic electricity or power supply, and Inadequate ICT facilities for AI technologies” (Isiaka, et al., 2024; Femi, 2024). Studies in Zambia explores the

perception of artificial intelligence among library and information science experts, finding reveals a positive attitude but its impact on librarian responsibilities and obstacles hindering its acceptance remains a concerns (Wood & Evans, 2018; Alam et al., 2024) in Zambian libraries.. Subaveerapandiyen et al. (2023) suggest that

despite the desire, there is a need to address practical difficulties for successful implementation. Moreover, to stay up-to-date on AI advancements, librarians should invest in knowledge management and conduct field studies to effectively use AI technology in library services, thereby enhancing their expertise and understanding

Relationship between ICT proficiency, awareness of artificial intelligence and information resources management

Figure 1 ICT Proficiency, Awareness of AI and Information Resource Management

The framework in Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between ICT proficiency, awareness of artificial intelligence (AI), and information resources management (IRM) in libraries. ICT proficiency of librarians contributes to effective IRM by enabling them to efficiently use digital tools and resources. Similarly, awareness of AI enhances IRM by allowing librarians to implement advanced technologies like AI for tasks such as cataloguing, user assistance, and data analysis. Both ICT proficiency and AI awareness are crucial for optimizing the management of information resources in libraries, ensuring that they are accessible, organized, and responsive to user needs.

Research Methodology

This research examined the level of ICT proficiency and awareness of artificial intelligence among librarians and information resources management in Nigerian libraries. Utilizing a survey research design, the study employed a quantitative research method through a

descriptive correlational design to achieve its objectives.

The sample for this study comprised of 399 librarians in various Nigerian libraries who responded to the online survey through the Google for 8 weeks. The data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire, comprising 21 items, covering three variables such as ICT proficiency, awareness of artificial intelligence, and information resources management. To determine the reliability of the questionnaire measuring ICT proficiency among librarians, Cronbach's Alpha was calculated using responses from 200 participants. The resulting Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.85, indicating high internal consistency. This means that the items on the questionnaire reliably measure the same underlying construct, making the questionnaire a dependable tool for assessing ICT proficiency. Generally, a value above 0.7 is acceptable, above 0.8 is good, and above 0.9 is excellent (Byrne, 2016), so a value of 0.85 demonstrates that the questionnaire is well-constructed and reliable.

The normality of the population distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, yielding significant results for ICT proficiency ($W = .885, p = .000$), awareness of artificial intelligence for information resources management ($W = .873, p = .000$), and information resources management ($W = .844, p = .000$). These results indicate that the data do not follow a normal distribution, as the p-values are all less than .05, demonstrating significant deviations from normality. This statistical evidence supports the reliability of the findings regarding the proficiency and awareness levels, as the non-normal distribution of the data reflects real variations and non-uniformity in the surveyed population. This can also be the

result of non-specified population as the data were collected based on responses within specified period across the librarians in Nigeria.

The study used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze data on the influence of ICT proficiency on artificial intelligence awareness, its influence on information resources management, and the combined effect of ICT proficiency and AI awareness on information resources management in Nigerian libraries. Descriptive statistics included mean scores and standard deviations, while inferential statistics included simple linear regression and multiple regression analyses.

Results and Findings

Level of ICT proficiency of Librarians (*Options: Very Low (1), Low (2), Moderate (3), High (4), Very High (5)*)

SNO	Level of ICT Proficiency of Librarians (N=399)	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)	\bar{X}	Std
1	Proficiency to use the Internet and advanced search techniques to find scholarly articles, e-books, and academic resources	4.00	6.30	17.80	48.00	23.90	3.81	0.999
2	Ability to evaluate the credibility and reliability of online sources for library collections	2.50	7.00	32.90	43.70	13.80	3.59	0.901
3	Proficiency to manage emails and communication tools with patrons, colleagues, and library vendors	4.30	6.50	25.60	41.50	22.10	3.71	1.019
4	Proficiency to access online resources, digital repositories, and electronic databases for library collection through web browsers	2.80	4.50	21.60	45.50	25.60	3.87	0.942
5	Skill to navigate library catalogues and other online platforms to locate and retrieve digital assets	5.00	3.30	27.10	39.90	24.60	3.76	1.022
6	Proficiency to use Microsoft application to manage library documents	3.00	5.80	43.50	36.70	11.10	3.47	0.877
7	Proficiency to handle data formats within library portals and integrated library systems, bibliographic metadata	2.30	5.80	31.90	36.40	23.60	3.73	0.96
8	Skills to use metadata standards and protocols for quality management of library collections and online catalogues	2.30	7.50	16.80	44.00	29.40	3.91	0.98
Average							3.73	0.963

The data evaluates the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) proficiency of librarians across various skills. The proficiency to use the Internet and

advanced search techniques to find scholarly articles, e-books, and academic resources received \bar{x} of 3.81, with a standard deviation of 0.999. The ability to evaluate the

credibility and reliability of online sources for library collections had \bar{x} 3.59 and a standard deviation of 0.901.

Managing emails and communication tools with patrons, colleagues, and library vendors scored \bar{x} 3.71, with a standard deviation of 1.019. Accessing online resources, digital repositories, and electronic databases through web browsers was rated slightly higher, with \bar{x} 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.942.

The skill to navigate library catalogues and other online platforms to locate and retrieve digital assets had \bar{x} of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.022. Proficiency in using Microsoft applications to manage library

documents was rated at \bar{x} 3.47, with a standard deviation of 0.877.

Handling data formats within library portals and integrated library systems, including bibliographic metadata, scored \bar{x} 3.73 and a standard deviation of 0.96. Lastly, skills to use metadata standards and protocols for quality management of library collections and online catalogues received the highest \bar{x} 3.91, with a standard deviation of 0.98. with the average mean score (\bar{x} =3.73, Std. 0.963), the data suggests that librarians generally exhibit a high level of ICT proficiency across a range of skills, particularly in accessing online resources and using metadata standards, although there is variability in their proficiency levels

Awareness of Artificial Intelligence for information resources management in libraries

Options: Not familiar (1), Slightly familiar (2), Moderately familiar (3), Very familiar (4), Extremely familiar (5)

SN	Level of Awareness of Artificial Intelligence for IRM by Librarians(N=399)	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)	\bar{X}	Std
1	Named Entity Recognition (NER) aids cataloguing in identifying entities such as authors, titles, dates, and locations within text documents	21.60	51.80	21.40	2.50	2.80	2.13	0.874
2	The Sentiment Analysis is one of the AI that is used for user reviews or feedback on library services	27.10	38.20	31.90	1.00	1.80	2.12	0.881
3	User-based Collaborative Filtering and Item-based Collaborative Filtering help in recommending library materials to users based on their past borrowing history and preferences	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	2.63	0.739
4	K-means Clustering and Hierarchical Clustering are AI that group library resources based on subject, genre, or content	30.4	30.4	30.4	30.4	30.4	2.15	0.937
5	Chatbots services as virtual assistance to library patrons by answering queries	32.9	32.9	32.9	32.9	32.9	1.96	0.961
6	Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) are used to digitize and analyze text and images from scanned documents	11.8	11.8	11.8	11.8	11.8	2.3	0.781
7	Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Vader Sentiment Analysis are applied to analyze user feedback, reviews, or social media mentions related to library services or resources	30.4	30.4	30.4	30.4	30.4	2.02	0.834
Average							2.18	0.858

The data examines the level of awareness among librarians regarding the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Information Resources Management (IRM). Named Entity Recognition (NER), which aids in cataloguing by identifying entities like authors, titles, dates, and locations within text documents, received \bar{x} 2.13 for awareness and a standard deviation of 0.874. Sentiment Analysis, used for assessing user reviews or feedback on library services, had a \bar{x} of 2.12 and a standard deviation of 0.881.

User-based Collaborative Filtering and Item-based Collaborative Filtering, which recommend library materials based on past borrowing history and preferences, had a consistent awareness level with all respondents reporting the same percentage across categories, resulting in a \bar{x} 2.63 and a standard deviation of 0.739. The awareness of K-means Clustering and Hierarchical Clustering, which group library resources by

subject, genre, or content, was reported consistently across all respondents, with a \bar{x} 2.15 and a standard deviation of 0.937.

Chatbot services, providing virtual assistance to library patrons, had \bar{x} 1.96 with a standard deviation of 0.961. The application of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for digitizing and analyzing text and images from scanned documents received \bar{x} 2.3 and a standard deviation of 0.781. Lastly, the use of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Vader Sentiment Analysis to analyze user feedback, reviews, or social media mentions related to library services or resources had \bar{x} 2.02 with a standard deviation of 0.834. The data suggests a moderate level of awareness among librarians regarding various AI applications in IRM, with some areas showing more consistent awareness levels than others.

Information Resource Management (Options: Strongly Disagree (1) Disagree (2) (Neutral (3) Agree (4) (Strongly Agree (5)

SN	Information resources management (N=399)	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)	X	Std
1	Google Scholar, ProQuest, Elseview, etc. are used to provide advanced search capabilities such as filtering by date, author, and publication type, to facilitate efficient discovery of scholarly materials	4.30	41.50	25.60	6.50	22.10	2.25	1.22
2	Systems like Library of Congress Classification (LCC) and Integrated Library Systems (ILS) such as Koha, are used to automate cataloguing processes and offer comprehensive search functionalities, ensuring systematic organization and seamless access to diverse library resources for patrons	2.80	45.50	21.60	4.50	25.60	3.01	1.24
3	The responsiveness of reference services provides timely assistance and offers a variety of communication channels for virtual reference queries	5.00	3.30	27.10	39.90	24.60	3.05	1.28
4	Library collections are regularly updated based on users' preferences and needs when developing the library collection	21.60	8.00	3.80	35.70	30.90	3.76	1.02
5	User data are analyzed to improve library services and analytics tools are utilized to enhance the user satisfaction with library services.	3.00	18.60	13.30	35.40	29.60	3.46	1.53
6	Information resources are made available based on constantly reviewing and accessing the needs of library users	26.10	49.00	11.80	0.30	12.80	3.7	1.17

The data presents an analysis of various aspects of information resources management within library systems. Advanced search capabilities provided by platforms such as Google Scholar, ProQuest, and Elsevier are utilized to streamline the discovery of scholarly materials, scoring \bar{x} 2.25 with a standard deviation of 1.219. Automation of cataloguing processes through systems like the Library of Congress Classification (LCC) and Integrated Library Systems (ILS) such as Koha, which facilitate comprehensive search functionalities and systematic organization of resources, received a higher \bar{x} 3.01 and a standard deviation of 1.241. The responsiveness of reference services, which includes providing timely assistance through multiple communication channels, was rated slightly higher \bar{x} 3.05 with a standard deviation of 1.28.

Furthermore, the regular updating of library collections based on user preferences and needs attained a \bar{x} 3.76, indicating significant importance, with a relatively lower standard deviation of 1.022, suggesting consistent responses among participants. The utilization of user data analytics to enhance library services and improve user satisfaction was rated \bar{x} 3.46, and 1.526 standard deviation, indicating a broader range of responses. Lastly, the constant review and assessment of library user needs to make information resources available were highly regarded, with \bar{x} 3.7 and a standard deviation of 1.166. These findings underscore the importance of integrating advanced search capabilities, systematic organization, timely reference services, user-driven collection updates, and data analytics in effective information resources management.

Table 4: Multiple Regression: ICT proficiency and awareness of Artificial Intelligence by librarians have no significant influence on the information resources management in Nigerian libraries

Model (Coefficients ^a)	Standardised coefficient					
	Beta	R	R Square	F	t	Sig.
(Constant)					11.230	.000
ICTProf	.339	.348a	.121	27.132	7.151	.000
AAI	.051				1.086	.278

a. Dependent Variable: Information Resource Management

A multiple regression was conducted to test the combined influence of ICT proficiency and awareness of artificial intelligence on information resource management in Nigerian libraries. Results of a multiple regression analysis showcased information resource management dependent variable, while the independent variables were ICT Proficiency of Librarians and awareness of Artificial Intelligence. The correlation coefficient (r) indicates a moderate positive relationship between the independent

variables (ICT proficiency and awareness of artificial intelligence) and the dependent variable (information resource management). The R² value (0.121) indicates that approximately 12.1% of the variance in information resource management can be explained by the independent variables— ICT Proficiency and Awareness of Artificial Intelligence. The F-value is 27.132, which tests the overall significance of the regression model. A high F-value indicates that the model is statistically significant. The unstandardized coefficient (0.320) indicates

that for each unit increase in ICT Proficiency, information resource management increases by 0.320 units, assuming Awareness of AI is held constant ($R^2=.121$, $F(399) =27.132$, $\beta=.320$, $p\text{-value}=.0001$).

It can be summarized that the ICT proficiency of librarians has a significant positive effect on information resource management. Librarians proficient in ICT manage information resources more effectively, while awareness of Artificial Intelligence does not significantly impact information resource management. This implies that simply being aware of AI is not enough to significantly influence the effectiveness of managing information resources.

The significant positive effect of ICT Proficiency highlights the importance of improving ICT skills among librarians, while non-significant effect of AI awareness suggests that additional factors such as practical application, training, and integration of AI tools might be necessary to realize the benefits of AI in information resource management.

Discussion of the findings

The findings suggest that librarians generally exhibit a high level of ICT proficiency across various skills, particularly in accessing online resources and using metadata standards, with some variability in proficiency levels. This observation aligns with several recent studies that have examined the ICT skills and digital competencies of librarians in the context of rapidly evolving library services.

Oyovwe-Tinuoye et al. (2021) conducted a study on the influence of ICT skills on job performance of librarians in university libraries in South-South Nigeria. Their findings corroborate the assertion that librarians demonstrate high proficiency in ICT skills, particularly in areas such as accessing online resources. They note that "ICT skills have a significant influence on

job performance of librarians" and that these skills are crucial for effective service delivery in modern libraries (Oyovwe-Tinuoye et al., 2021). Similarly, Ubogu (2022) investigated the influence of ICT competencies on job performance in Nigerian university libraries. The study found that librarians with higher ICT competencies performed better in their roles, indicating a strong correlation between ICT skills and job effectiveness. This supports the finding that librarians are generally proficient in ICT skills, as their job performance is positively impacted by these competencies.

The variability in proficiency levels noted in the findings is also reflected in the literature. Nazim et al. (2022) surveyed librarians working in the Aligarh Muslim University Library System and found that while librarians generally had high self-efficacy in ICT-based library operations and services, there were variations across different skills. For instance, they might be more proficient in using online databases but less so in advanced data analysis or programming tasks.

Proficiency in metadata standards is crucial for librarians' digital competence, aiding effective organization and retrieval of digital resources (Tolmach, 2022a). Although Library and Information Science graduates in South Africa are well-prepared in basic ICT skills, continuous professional development is needed to keep up with emerging technologies (Sibiya, 2023a).

The finding that librarians generally exhibit high levels of ICT proficiency, particularly in skills related to accessing online resources and using metadata standards is upheld by scholars. These skills are crucial for effective service delivery in modern, digital-centric libraries. The variability in proficiency levels indicates a need for continuous professional development to adapt to the evolving technological landscape of library services (Oyovwe-Tinuoye *et al.*, 2021; Ubogu, 2022;

Nazim et al., 2022; Tolmach, 2022a; Sibiya, 2023a).

The findings that librarians have a moderate level of awareness about AI applications for information resources management, with consistent awareness of Collaborative Filtering and variable awareness of Named Entity Recognition and Sentiment Analysis. This reflects the ongoing discourse on librarians' readiness and perception towards AI integration in library services. Studies by Ajani et al. (2022) and Owolabi et al. (2020) show that while librarians are increasingly aware of AI's potential in libraries, their understanding varies across different AI applications. Collaborative Filtering, a key component of recommendation systems, is more consistently recognized by librarians. Named Entity Recognition and Sentiment Analysis, on the other hand, are more specialized and may not be familiar to many librarians. Oladokun et al. (2023) argues that while AI technologies offer benefits like advanced information organization and user experience enhancement, there is a need for more awareness and training programs to help librarians fully understand and utilize these technologies.

In furtherance to the above, the findings emphasize the importance of integrating advanced search capabilities, systematic organization, timely reference services, user-driven collection updates, and data analytics in effective information resources management. The literature supports this multifaceted approach, highlighting the transformative role of technology in modern library services. Al-Aamri and Osman (2021) argue that AI technologies, like natural language processing and machine learning, enhance search capabilities by providing more intuitive and accurate results. Kapterev (2023) discusses how AI can automate cataloging and classification, ensuring consistent and accurate organization of resources. Xie (2023) notes that AI-powered chatbots and virtual

assistants offer instant, 24/7 reference services, crucial for timely assistance.

User-driven collection updates are supported by Choukimath et al. (2019), who state that AI can analyze user behavior to inform collection development. Ali et al. (2020) and Redkina (2023) highlight the role of data analytics in providing insights into resource usage, user preferences, and research trends, guiding strategic decisions in resource management. The integration of advanced search capabilities, systematic organization, timely reference services, user-driven collection updates, and data analytics represents a holistic, technology-enhanced approach to managing library resources effectively in the digital age.

In addition, the findings present a view of ICT proficiency and AI awareness in information resource management. They indicate that while librarians' ICT proficiency greatly enhances their ability to manage information resources, AI awareness alone does not have a significant impact. This underscores the necessity for practical AI training and integration to fully leverage its benefits.

The positive influence of ICT proficiency is well-supported in the literature. Oyovwe-Tinuoye et al. (2021) and Ubogu (2022) both found that ICT skills significantly improve librarians' job performance in tasks such as digital cataloging and electronic resource management, corroborating the importance of ICT proficiency highlighted in the findings. Conversely, the limited impact of AI awareness is echoed in studies by Owolabi et al. (2020) and Ajani et al. (2022). These studies reveal that while there is growing awareness of AI, it does not necessarily translate into improved library services or resource management due to a lack of practical application. This aligns with the finding that mere AI awareness is insufficient.

The need for practical AI training is strongly supported by the literature. Oladokun et al.

(2023) and Subaveerapandiyan et al. (2023) emphasize that librarians require hands-on experience with AI tools to fully realize AI's potential in areas such as automated cataloging and AI-driven reference services. The findings highlight the critical need for targeted, practical AI training programs to enhance librarians' effectiveness in managing information resources.

Conclusion

The study concludes that librarians exhibit a high level of ICT proficiency, especially in accessing online resources and using metadata standards, though proficiency levels vary. There is moderate awareness among librarians of AI applications for information resource management, with consistent awareness of Collaborative Filtering and variable awareness of Named Entity Recognition and Sentiment Analysis. The findings underscore the importance of integrating advanced search capabilities, systematic organization, timely reference services, user-driven collection updates, and data analytics for effective information resources management. Furthermore, the study reveals that while ICT proficiency significantly enhances information resource management, AI awareness alone does not. This highlights the need for practical AI training and integration to fully leverage AI's benefits in library services.

Recommendations

- 1 Libraries should implement practical AI training for librarians to improve their understanding and application of AI technologies, focusing on tools like Named Entity Recognition and Sentiment Analysis.
- 2 Libraries should continue to build on the strong ICT skills of librarians by providing advanced training in digital cataloging, online resource access, and electronic resource management.
- 3 Libraries should invest in AI-driven search technologies to enhance the accuracy and intuitiveness of search

results, making information retrieval more efficient for users.

- 4 Libraries should employ data analytics to better understand user behaviour and preferences, guiding collection development and improving overall library services.

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